

THE ROLE OF GAMES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract:

This article aims to the role of games in teaching, the object of the study was the methods of language learning, the suggests of this research, arguments of manuals writers;

Key words and phrases: language, role of game, learning language, resources, communication, vocabulary, classroom atmosphere, quizzes, pedagogical value, competition, communicative competence;

Language improvement is easy, if we enjoy doing it. In fact everything is easy in this world, if we love to do it. So for improving your spoken English you need to enjoy the learning process. There are number of resources available online, which makes your learning process easy. The best way to do it, is by using English games. Check out online for a plethora of material for English improvement. The net provides a plethora of information about various activities and ways to Improve spoken English. But you need to find the one that appeals and draw your attention. That is important so as to keep you intact with the learning process. Try English games like spoken Hangman, Vocabulary games, quizzes, buzzer rounds ect.at home to fasten up for process. Once you have opted for ESL, then be sure of the fact that you have made a very good decision. I will be working on to incorporate as many games as possible in this blog, so as to help my readers get the most out of it. Apart from these, there are many spoken English articles, which could be very useful. The audio courses available on the net are helpful to make your self-accustomed to the way the English is spoken. Apart from that the games which the site provides are very useful.

English games are the best way to enjoy the process of English learning. You can play alone, or any of your friends can accompany you in these games. Games like grammar quizzes, Hangman, ect. makes to strive for more. And you compete to know more and more. It is a nice way to improve your spoken vocal capability. Not to mention that it enhances your vocabulary also. Internet is wide, and unlimited, search for resources, but stick to those which you like and

are able to understand. Because that will help you to gain confidence. Sometimes too many resources also can hamper your progress of English learning, as you could be confused regarding which to choose. But narrowing your search to a few genuine and authentic English teaching sites, can boost your performance in an amazing way. Good English speaking skill are required in every aspect of our lives. We all know that English is the language that unifies the world, as it is the language known to maximum number of individuals around the globe. Today if we want a decent job, want to impress a girl, or desire respect in society, everything circles to our speaking skill.

Games have been shown to have advantages and effectiveness in learning vocabulary in various ways. First, games bring in relaxation and fun for students, thus help them learn and retain new words more easily. Second, games usually involve friendly competition and they keep learners interested. These create the motivation for learners of English in a flexible, communicative way. Therefore, the role of games in teaching and learning vocabulary cannot be denied. However, in order to achieve the most from vocabulary games, it is essential that suitable games are chosen. Whenever a game is to be conducted, the number of students, proficiency level, cultural context, timing learning topic, and the classroom settings are factory that should be taken into account.

Many experienced textbook and methodology manuals writers have argued that games are not just time – filling activities but have a great education value. S. M. Silver holds that most language games make learners use the language instead of thinking about learning the correct form [1979:2]. He also says that games should be treated as central not peripheral to the foreign language teaching program. A similar opinion is express by Richard – Amato, who believes games to be fun but warns against overlooking their pedagogical value, particularly in foreign language teaching.

There are many advantages of using games. “Games can lower anxiety, thus making the acquisition of input more likely” [1:147]. They are highly motivating and entertaining, and they can give shy students more opportunity to express their opinions and feelings [2:118]. They also enable learners to acquire new experiences within a foreign language which are not always possible during a typical lesson. Furthermore, to quote Richard – Amato, they, “add diversion to the regular classroom activities”, break the ice, “[but also] they are used to introduce new ideas” [1:147]. In the easy, relaxed atmosphere which is created by using games, students remember things faster and better [3:218]. S. M. Silvers says many teachers are enthusiastic about using games as “a teaching

device,” yet they often perceive games as mere time – fillers, “a break from the monotony of drilling ” or frivolous activities. He also claims that many teachers often overlook the fact that in a relaxed atmosphere, real learning takes place, and students use the language they have been exposed to and have practiced earlier [4:29]. Further support comes from Zdybiewska, who believes games to be a good way of practicing language for they provide a model of what learners will use the language for in real life in the future. Games encourage, entertain, teach, and promote fluency. If not for any of these reasons, they should be used just because they help students see beauty in a foreign language and not just problems that at times seem overwhelming.

In conclusion, learning vocabulary through games is one effective and interesting way that can be applied in any classrooms. The results of this research suggest that games are used not only for mere fun, but more importantly, for the useful practice and review of language lessons, thus leading toward the goal of improving learners’ communicative competence.

References:

1. Ташланова, Н. Д. (2019). Развитие критического мышления студентов в вузах. Проблемы современной науки и образования, (11-2 (144)), 63-64.
2. Tashlanova, N. (2021). The essence of collaborative approach in learning a language. Scientific progress, 2(8), 281-286.
3. Tashlanova, N. D. (2019). Development of critical thinking of students in universities. Problems of modern science and education,(11-2), 144, 22-28.
4. Djuraevna, T. N. (2022). Language Teaching Methodology: Tradition and Modernity. Central Asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture, 3(2), 41-51.
5. Ташланова, Н. Д. (2019). Использование опорной технологии в обучении русского языка. Экономика и социум, (9), 289-292.
6. Ташланова, Н. Д. (2019). Применение различных видов лекций для развития критического мышления студентов в высших учебных заведениях. Экономика и социум, (8), 220-224.
7. Ташланова, Н. Д. (2018). Формирование навыков при выполнении самостоятельных работ студентов в высших учебных заведениях. Мировая наука, (4), 238-240.
8. Ташланова, Н. Д. (2018). Эффективное использование современных компьютерных технологий на уроках иностранных языков. Экономика и социум, (11), 907-910.

9. Ташланова, Н. Д. (2022). Особенности Методических Приемов Изучения Второго Иностранного Языка. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(9), 1-11.
10. Djuraevna, T. N. (2022). Correlation of Didactics, Linguodidactics and Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 12, 7-16.
11. Djuraevna, T. N. (2022). Correlation of Didactics, Linguodidactics and Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 12, 7-16.
12. Ташланова, Н. Д. (2019). Использование опорной технологии в обучении русского языка. *Экономика и социум*, (9), 289-292.
13. Djuraevna, T. N. (2022). Correlation of Didactics, Linguodidactics and Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 12, 7-16.
14. Ташланова, Н. Д. (2018). Эффективное использование игровых технологий в процессе обучения. *Форум молодых ученых*, (4), 1419-1421.
15. Tashlanova, N. Teaching special disciplines with innovative technologies.
16. Н.Д.Ташланова, (2022). Использование дистанционного обучения в системе высшего образования. *Research Focus*, 1(2), 333-339.

